

SHORT NOTES

SWIETENINE, THE NON-BITTER PRINCIPLE OF THE SEEDS OF *SWIETENIA MACROPHYLLA* KING

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Swietenia macrophylla King (Fam. *Meliaceae*) contains in its seeds a neutral non-bitter principle, swietenine and a bitter component, swietenolide. Earlier it was demonstrated by the present investigators that swietenine, m.p. 260° (decomp), $[\alpha]_D^{20} -168^{\circ}$ (chloroform) was an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated lactone (which can be opened reversibly) having a tertiary hydroxyl, a six-ring ketone and a methoxyl group (Chakrabartty and Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 117; 1955, 32, 179). It was also reported that the compound on selenium dehydrogenation formed a mixture of polyalkyl naphthalene derivatives.

The complete formulation of this non-bitter principle could not be worked out earlier because of the difficulties of assessing its correct molecular weight. The latter determined by Rast, by Beckmann's method or by titration was not satisfactory. The molecular weight has now been determined by X-ray analysis which indicates it to be 565. On the basis of this datum the formula of swietenine appears as $C_{32}H_{42}O_9$. The methoxyl function is now found to be associated with a methoxycarbonyl. A careful inspection of the infrared spectrum of the non-bitter principle in Nujol (peaks at 1506, 1030 and 877 cm^{-1}) and its UV spectrum (strong absorption near about 210 m μ ; ϵ nearly 32,000), suggests the presence of a furyl group, which also follows from the following evidences :

(a) The compound develops a pink coloration with hydrochloric acid and *p*-dimethylamino-benzaldehyde (Ehrlich's reagent). This is indicative of the presence of a β -substituted furan in the compound.

(b) During ozonolysis, swietenine generates formic acid like columbin (Barton and Elad, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2085) (characterised as its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester, m.p. 84°). The other product of ozonolysis lacks the infrared frequency which corresponds to that of a furan ring (peaks at 1506, 1030 and 877 cm^{-1} in Nujol).

(c) Proton magnetic resonance spectrum (Corey *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 1024) shows proton resonance at -113 and -62 cps, these n.m.r. signals being characteristic of a β -monosubstituted furan.

The compound has been further shown to be an ester of tiglic acid which is liberated during caustic potash fusion at 258° , as also during hydrolysis under mild conditions.

Swietenine contains five $-\text{C}\cdot\text{CH}_3$ groupings and does not react with lead tetra-acetate, thus showing that the ketonic and tertiary hydroxyl groups are not vicinal. It does not consume periodic acid showing the absence of an isolated double bond (Chatterjee *et al.*, *Ann. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 878) in the compound.

